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Interaction mechanisms between C15 Laves phase clusters and $\langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ dislocation loops in BCC-Fe: An atomistic perspective

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ABSTRACT

Small C15 Laves phase clusters are extended interstitial defects that form during collision cascades in body-centered cubic (BCC) iron. Although their stability has been confirmed by ab initio calculations up to a certain size, their interactions with other irradiation-induced defects, such as dislocation loops, remain poorly understood. In this study, we use molecular dynamics (MD) and molecular statics (MS) simulations to investigate the interaction mechanisms between C15 clusters and $\frac{1}{2}\langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ prismatic dislocation loops in BCC-Fe at elevated temperatures (600–1000 K). By systematically varying the relative size and positioning of these defects, we identify three distinct interaction modes: absorption, repulsion, and confinement. Absorption events lead to a range of outcomes depending on the interaction geometry, including complete merging into $\frac{1}{2}\langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ or $\langle 1\ 0\ 0 \rangle$ dislocation loops, or the formation of mixed clusters. Stress field analysis reveals that the nature of these interactions is governed by the overlap of elastic fields, with repulsive or attractive behavior arising from the alignment of tensile and compressive regions. These findings provide new atomistic insights into the role of C15 clusters in microstructural evolution under irradiation and offer valuable input parameters for higher-scale modeling techniques such as object kinetic Monte Carlo (OKMC).

Introduction

Radiation damage in body-centered cubic (BCC) iron as a based element of structural material of nuclear reactor has been devoted to many studies for several decades. The multi-scale method is a well-known approach to investigating the degrading of metals under irradiation [1]. Among the available methods, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations have been extensively used to study the radiation response of materials. MD simulations are particularly effective in explaining the primary stages of radiation damage. This method uniquely captures displacement cascade damage (collision cascades), which occurs on the picosecond timescale due to neutron collisions with crystal atoms. These simulations demonstrate the formation and evolution of defects, such as self-interstitial atoms (SIAs), vacancies, defect clusters, and dislocation loops [2–6]. Additionally, MD offers insights into the interactions between collision cascades and pre-existing microstructural features—such as voids, grain boundaries, dislocation loops, and vacancy clusters [2,7–13]—as well as into the interactions among these features themselves [14–16]. Beyond simulating primary damage through single cascades, MD simulations have been utilized to investigate successive overlapping cascades, enabling the characterization of defect

accumulation under increasing radiation doses [17–19]. While such simulations can effectively represent defect evolution at room temperature, their applicability at higher temperatures is limited. At elevated temperatures, rapid defect diffusion and the inherently short timescales of MD—restricted to tens of picoseconds between successive cascades—can lead to inaccuracies in simulating defect accumulation. Object kinetic Monte Carlo (OKMC) simulations provide a solution to this limitation by extending the simulation timescale between successive cascades [20–23]. In OKMC, defects are treated as individual objects, with all potential interactions and reactions predefined to accurately model microstructural evolution. MD simulations serve as a valuable source of input data for OKMC, providing information such as the number of defects generated by single cascades, diffusion parameters for both point and extended defects, and their interactions.

In BCC-Fe, extended defects such as dislocation loops with $\frac{1}{2}\langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ and $\langle 1\ 0\ 0 \rangle$ Burgers vectors, C15 laves clusters, vacancy clusters, and voids form during irradiation. The evolution of these defects and their interactions can degrade the mechanical properties of iron [24]. Characterizing the interactions between these defects is crucial to provide input parameters for larger time-scale methods. In α -iron crystals, $\frac{1}{2}\langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loops are glissile and can move easily within the material,

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whereas $\langle 1\ 0\ 0 \rangle$ loops and C15 Laves clusters remain immobile. The interactions of $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loops with $\langle 1\ 0\ 0 \rangle$ loops and voids have been investigated in several studies [25,26]. Absorption, repulsion, and confinement have been observed when $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ are located in various spatial positions relative to $\langle 1\ 0\ 0 \rangle$ loops [25].

C15 Laves phase clusters are extended defects formed during collision cascades in Fe [27,28]. Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations have shown that C15 clusters, up to a certain size, are the most stable among various types of interstitial clusters [29]. Molecular dynamics simulations indicate that as the size of C15 clusters grows, they primarily collapse into $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loops at 500 K [30]. The interaction of dislocation loops and C15-clusters has not been studied yet. In this study, we investigate the interaction between C15 clusters and $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ prismatic dislocation loops (PDLs) using molecular dynamics simulations. By activating loop movement at 600 K, the interactions were tracked. To interpret the results, the atomic stress distribution of the defects were analyzed.

Methods

To characterize the interaction between C15 laves clusters and $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loops in Fe, the evolution of systems containing these interstitial clusters was studied using MD simulations. Initially, a C15-like cluster and a prismatic dislocation loop with a $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ Burgers vector were created in a simulation box containing α -Fe atoms with a lattice constant $a = 2.85 \text{ \AA}$ (Fig. 1a). Two different box sizes including $8.56 \times 8.56 \times 8.56 \text{ nm}^3$ and $11.42 \times 11.42 \times 11.42 \text{ nm}^3$ were used. We investigated the interaction between C15 clusters containing 11 and 40 SIAs and $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loops containing 16, 48, 100, and 300 SIAs. The C15 clusters and $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loops were inserted into the simulation box at various relative positions. To determine these relative positions, a $(1\ 1\ 1)$ plane tangent to the outer atomic layer of the C15 cluster was defined (Fig. 1a). A Z' -axis was then aligned along the glide direction of the $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loop, passing through the center of mass of the C15 cluster, with the origin located in $(1\ 1\ 1)$ plane (Fig. 1a). This setup created a cylindrical coordinate system based on $X'[2\bar{1}\bar{1}]$, $Y'[0\bar{1}\bar{1}]$, and $Z'[111]$. In this configuration, Δr represents the radial distance from the center of the loop to the center of mass of the C15 cluster, and Δl is the vertical distance from the PDL to the atomic surface of the C15 cluster, as shown in Fig. 1.

After inserting the microstructures, energy minimization was performed using the conjugate gradient (CG) method. To activate the motion of the $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loops, MD simulations were conducted at 600 K under the NPT ensemble for up to 6 ns for absorption and repulsion interactions, and up to 10 ns for confinement cases. In specific cases, after the interaction at 600 K, the temperature was increased to 1000 K

for an additional 6 ns. It should be noted that theoretical studies have shown that at elevated temperatures, increasingly anisotropic elasticity in bcc-Fe makes $\langle 1\ 0\ 0 \rangle$ loops thermodynamically favorable [31]. Among the various interatomic potentials evaluated—including EAM (M07-B) [32], ABOP [30], and recent ML-based potentials [33,34]—the M07-B potential has been shown to best capture this behavior at high temperatures. For this reason, and given our simulation temperature range of 600–1000 K, we employed M07-B in this study. OVITO software was used to visualize the dislocation loops and defects [35].

To interpret this interaction, the virial atomic stress distribution of C15 clusters and $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loops were calculated separately using molecular statics (MS). The virial contribution to the per-atom stress tensor was determined based on the methodology described in Ref. [36]. To analyze the stress field in the glide direction of the loop ($[1\ 1\ 1]$), the Cauchy stress tensor was transformed to a new coordinate system using the transformation rules outlined in Ref. [37]. The basis vectors for the new coordinate system are defined as: $X' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}(2, -1, -1)$, $Y' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}(0, 1, -1)$ and $Z' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}(1, 1, 1)$.

Results

To investigate the interaction between C15 clusters and PDLs, we considered C15 clusters of varying sizes placed at the center of the simulation box, with the dislocation loop positioned at different relative locations characterized by Δr and Δl (Fig. 1a). Since $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ prismatic dislocation loops are mobile, elevating the temperature to 600 K provides the necessary activation energy for these loops to move freely within defect-free regions. By tracking the evolution of the $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loop at 600 K, the interactions with C15 clusters were investigated.

When the $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loop is located within a specific range of Δr and Δl , it can easily glide toward the C15 cluster and combine with it. Fig. 2 presents a snapshot of a typical absorption event, where a C15 cluster with 11 SIAs and a $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loop containing 300 SIAs are initially positioned at $\Delta r = 23.31 \text{ \AA}$ and $\Delta l = 14.7 \text{ \AA}$ relative to each other. The range of Δr and Δl that allow a $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loop to combine with a C15 cluster are shown in Fig. 3 for various sizes of C15 clusters and PDLs. This figure indicates that both Δr and Δl increase with the size of the loop. We identified a rule of thumb for this interaction across all cases: the combination of defect clusters occurs if ΔA satisfies $1 \leq \Delta A \leq 0.8$, where $\Delta A = \frac{|A_l - A_c|}{A_l}$. Here A_l is the area of the loop, and A_c is the area of the interface between the projection of the loop and the C15 cluster in the (111) plane (Fig. 1b). It should be noted that the condition for Δl must also be satisfied in this scenario. The type of cluster formed by the combination of a PDL and a C15 cluster depends on the sizes of the two

Fig. 1. a) schematic showing the relative position of a $1/2 \langle 1\ 1\ 1 \rangle$ loop with respect to a C15 cluster, defined by Δl (vertical distance from the dislocation loop to the atomic surface of the C15 cluster) and Δr (radial distance from the center of the loop to the center of mass of the C15 cluster). b) The area of the interface (A_c) between the projection of the loop and the C15 cluster in the (111) plane.

Fig. 2. Snapshot showing the absorption interaction between a C15 cluster with 11 SIAs and a 1/2 $\langle 111 \rangle$ loop containing 300 SIAs. The blue region represents the surface mesh of the C15 cluster, providing a visualization of its structure. Panels (a) and (b) illustrate the relative positions of the two objects from different perspectives at $t = 0$ ps. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Absorption regions (Δl and Δr ranges) where 1/2 $\langle 111 \rangle$ PDLs containing 16, 48, 100, and 300 SIAs can absorb C15 clusters containing (a) 11 SIAs and (b) 40 SIAs.

Fig. 4. Four different absorption mechanisms observed before and after recombination, when a C15 cluster with 40 SIAs interacts with a 1/2 $\langle 111 \rangle$ PDL containing 48 SIAs at varying Δr values.

defects and Δr . We observed five distinct outcomes for the absorption cases across all tested C15 and $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop sizes. For example, four of these five possible outcomes are illustrated in Fig. 4, where a C15 cluster with 40 SIAs interacts with a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop containing 48 SIAs at various Δr values.

When the resulting cluster combination is a $\langle 100 \rangle$ loop, we classify the interaction as *absorption type 1*, which occurs in the initial absorption range of Δr (see Fig. 3b and Fig. 4a). Notably, this type of interaction was not observed for other C15 and $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop size combinations (see Table 1). Fig. 4b and 4d show cases of partial absorption, where the outcome is a larger $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop and a small SIAs cluster. The difference between these two partial absorption outcomes lies in the radial distance Δr . In Fig. 4b, where Δr is smaller, the dislocation loop was repelled by the remaining SIA cluster after absorption and glided in the opposite direction compared to its initial glide direction (*absorption type 2*). In contrast, in Fig. 4d, where the loop is initially located radially farther from the C15 cluster, the loop absorbs part of the C15 SIAs and continues its movement in the same direction (*absorption type 4*). Fig. 4c shows another outcome: the merged configuration of the $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop and the C15 cluster after 6 ns at 600 K (*absorption type 3*). Additionally, we observed the formation of complete dislocation loops, where all SIAs from the C15 cluster joined the dislocation loop, for loops with sizes of 100 SIAs and 300 SIAs (*absorption type 5*; see Fig. 2). Table 1 summarizes which of these five types of interactions occurs for different sizes of C15 clusters and $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDLs. To determine the final shape of the C15–dislocation loop mixture in *absorption type 3*, we increased the temperature from 600 K to 1000 K and extended the simulation for an additional 6 ns. The results are shown in Fig. 5 for selected examples. These results indicate that the final configuration is either a complete $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop (Fig. 5a and c) or a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop with a small SIA cluster (Fig. 5b). Notably, only these two outcomes were observed for all mixed C15–loop SIA clusters after increasing the temperature to 1000 K.

By increasing Δl or decreasing Δr from the specified absorption region in Fig. 3, repulsion between loops and the C15 cluster may occur (Fig. 6). Fig. 6 shows snapshots of this evolution for a small value of Δr . It should be noted that when Δl is within the range of the absorption region and Δr decreases such that the C15 cluster appears aligned within the loop in the $[111]$ projection (even though they are spatially separate; see Fig. 6), repulsion is consistently observed for all types of C15 clusters and dislocation loops studied in this paper.

Conversely, by increasing Δr beyond the determined area in Fig. 3, such that the C15 cluster appears completely outside the loop in the $[111]$ projection (Fig. 7a), the movement of the $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop becomes confined to the region below the C15 cluster. Fig. 7a–c illustrates this confinement for up to 10 ns at 600 K, where a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop with 48 SIAs is confined by a C15 cluster with 40 SIAs. To assess the strength of

this confinement, simulations were performed at higher temperatures (800 K and 1000 K), where the thermal diffusion of the $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop is greater. Even under these conditions, the confinement persisted (Fig. 7d and 7e). This behavior was observed for all types of C15 clusters and dislocation loops studied. Even a small C15 cluster containing 11 SIAs can effectively confine PDLs with up to 100 SIAs at 1000 K, maintaining confinement for at least 10 ns.

Discussion

We observed absorption, repulsion, and confinement of $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loops by immobile C15 Laves clusters (Fig. 2, Fig. 6, and Fig. 7), which occurred due to the thermal diffusion of $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loops at elevated temperatures (600–1000 K). These three types of interactions have also been reported for $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loops and immobile $\langle 100 \rangle$ loops in thermal diffusion simulations conducted using discrete dislocation dynamics (DDD) [25]. Elastic interactions play a key role in governing these behaviors [25].

Analyzing the atomic stress fields of the $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loops and the C15 Laves clusters can provide valuable information about the mechanisms governing the observed interactions. Although analytically calculating the elastic interaction energy between these objects is complex, qualitative understanding can be obtained by considering stress field interactions similar to those observed between dislocations. The interaction mechanism is governed by the minimization of the system's elastic energy. When the stress fields of extended defects overlap (provided one or both are mobile), their interaction depends on the characteristics of the stress fields and their ability to reduce the total system energy. If the overlapping regions of the stress fields are both compressive or both tensile, the elastic energy increases, resulting in a repulsive interaction. Conversely, if one stress field is compressive and the other tensile, the elastic energy decreases, leading to an attractive or absorptive interaction. Such behavior has been previously explained for the interaction between dislocations with the same or opposite signs [38]. Therefore, to interpret the interactions between $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDLs and C15 Laves clusters, we analyzed the stress fields along the $[111]$ direction. Molecular statics was employed to calculate the stress fields of $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loops and C15 clusters. Fig. 8 shows the X'Y' and Z' components of the stress fields for both the C15 cluster and the $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop. In Fig. 8a, the stress field of the $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop in the $[111]$ direction exhibits a bipolar shape. The negative (compressive) stress field extends along the loop in the $[111]$ direction, while the positive (tensile) stress field appears as a small ring surrounding the loop. In contrast, Fig. 8c shows a semi-spherical stress field generated by the C15 cluster in the $[111]$ direction. The core of the semi-spherical stress field of the C15 cluster exhibits a mix of positive and negative stress, surrounded by a predominantly negative stress field. When these defects are placed opposite each other, similar to the relative configuration shown in Fig. 6a and b, their repulsion can be understood by considering the stress fields of the loop and C15 cluster (Fig. 8a and c), where identical stress fields (negative-negative) overlap. However, by increasing the radial distance and decreasing the vertical distance between these two extended defects, the likelihood of overlap between the positive stress field of one defect and the negative stress field of the other increases (Fig. 9). This overlap results in an absorption mechanism driven by the minimization of elastic energy.

By increasing Δr beyond the specified absorption area shown in Fig. 3, and in cases where $\Delta A = 1$, confinement of the loop movement was observed (Fig. 7) in the region below the C15 cluster. The confinement of dislocation movement observed beneath the C15 cluster might be explained by an interaction between the positive stress field of the prismatic dislocation loop and the long-range, weaker compressive stress field of the C15 cluster. Fig. 7 illustrates that even at an elevated temperature of 1000 K, the PDL remains confined, indicating a relatively high binding energy between the dislocation loops and the C15 Laves cluster. This suggests that the elastic confinement of $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDLs by

Table 1

The type of absorption interaction (1, 2, 3, 4 and 5) and the related Δr based on size of C15 clusters and $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDLs.

C15 size	loop size (number of SIAs)			
	16	48	100	300
11SIAs	$3(\Delta r = 9.32\text{\AA}, 13.98\text{\AA})$	$3(\Delta r = 10.68\text{\AA}, 13.98\text{\AA}), 4(\Delta r = 16.32\text{\AA})$	$5(\Delta r = 13.98\text{\AA}, 16.32\text{\AA}, 17.60\text{\AA}), 3(\Delta r = 20.98\text{\AA})$	$5(\Delta r = 20.98\text{\AA}, 23.31\text{\AA}, 27.97\text{\AA}), 3(\Delta r = 30.31\text{\AA})$
40SIAs	$3(\Delta r = 9.32\text{\AA}, 13.98\text{\AA}, 16.32\text{\AA})$	$1(\Delta r = 10.68\text{\AA}), 2(\Delta r = 13.98\text{\AA}), 3(\Delta r = 16.32\text{\AA}), 4(\Delta r = 20.98\text{\AA})$	$2(\Delta r = 13.98\text{\AA}), 5(\Delta r = 16.32\text{\AA}, 17.60\text{\AA}), 3(\Delta r = 20.98\text{\AA}, 23.31\text{\AA}), 4(\Delta r = 24.56\text{\AA})$	$2(\Delta r = 20.98\text{\AA}), 5(\Delta r = 23.31\text{\AA}), 3(\Delta r = 27.97\text{\AA}, 30.31\text{\AA}, 31.53\text{\AA})$

Fig. 5. The evolution of C15–PDL loop mixtures over time and temperature in *absorption type 3* for: (a) a C15 cluster with 11 SIAs and a loop containing 16 SIAs at $\Delta r = 13.98\text{\AA}$; (b) a C15 cluster with 40 SIAs and a loop containing 16 SIAs at $\Delta r = 16.32\text{\AA}$; (c) a C15 cluster with 40 SIAs and a loop containing 300 SIAs at $\Delta r = 31.53\text{\AA}$.

Fig. 6. Snapshot showing the repulsion interaction between a C15 cluster with 11 SIAs and a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop containing 100 SIAs. The blue region represents the surface mesh of the C15 cluster, providing a visualization of its structure. Panels (a) and (b) illustrate the relative positions of the two objects from different perspectives at $t = 0$ ps. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

C15 clusters could serve as a mechanism contributing to the stabilization of experimentally observed rafts of dislocation loops. If Δr is increased further to the point where there is no overlap between their stress fields, $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDL can move freely without being influenced by the presence of the C15 cluster.

When a C15 cluster combines with a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDL, various outcomes are possible. To understand these results, it is important to consider the formation energy of interstitial clusters in BCC iron. Based on DFT calculations, C15 clusters up to a size of approximately 50 SIAs are the most stable interstitial clusters [29], whereas MS simulations underestimate this value to around 30 SIAs [18]. After combination, we did not observe the mixed defects collapsing into $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loops when the total number of SIAs in the C15 cluster and the loop was below 30 at 600 K, even after 6 ns. However, in this case, increasing the temperature to 1000 K led to the collapse of the mixed defects into a $1/2 \langle 211 \rangle$

dislocation loop. When the total number of interstitials in the combined cluster exceeds 50, the transformation of the mixture into a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop was observed. These results are consistent with DFT calculations, which show that $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDLs are the most stable clusters when their size exceeds 50 SIAs.

In cases where the sizes of the C15 cluster and the $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop are 40 and 48 SIAs, respectively, the possible outcome of their combination can be either a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop or a $\langle 100 \rangle$ loop (Fig. 4). Regarding the formation of $\langle 100 \rangle$ loops, this may represent a new mechanism distinct from those reported in previous studies [30,39]. In these studies, $\langle 100 \rangle$ loops were shown to form either through the interaction of two $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loops [39] or by the collapse of large C15 clusters [30]. Ref.[30] explains that $\langle 100 \rangle$ loops are energetically very close in stability to $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loops when using the M07-B potential, which is suitable for simulations at high temperatures. It is noteworthy that in this case, the

Fig. 7. Snapshot showing the confinement interaction between a C15 cluster with 48 SIAs and a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop containing 40 SIAs. The blue region represents the surface mesh of the C15 cluster, providing a visualization of its structure. Panels (a) and (b) depict the relative positions of the two objects from different perspectives at $t = 0$ ps. Panels (c), (d), and (e) show the position of the dislocation at 600 K, 800 K, and 1000 K, respectively, after 10,000 ps. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Visualization of the virial atomic stress distribution components for high-stress atoms: (a) Z' and (b) $X'Y'$ components in a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ dislocation loop containing 100 SIAs; (c) Z' and (d) $X'Y'$ components in a C15 cluster with 40 SIAs.

combined cluster contains 88 SIAs, which is close to the size at which DFT calculations predict that $\langle 100 \rangle$ loops become more stable than C15 clusters.

Conclusions

MD and MS simulations were conducted to characterize the interaction between C15 clusters and $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDLs. Depending on the size of the defects and their relative positions, three types of interactions were identified:

1. Repulsion: Repulsion between the defects was observed due to the interaction of their stress fields in the glide direction of the loop. It

should be mentioned that even a very small C15 cluster (with 11 SIAs) was capable of repelling a significantly larger $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDL (with 300 SIAs)

2. Absorption: When a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDL overcomes the repulsive interaction and moves into the close vicinity of a C15 cluster (satisfying the Δl condition), it can combine with the C15 cluster under specific relative positions. For absorption to occur, the area of the interface between the loop and the C15 cluster in the (111) plane (A_{lc}) must not exceed 20 % of the loop's area.

Five distinct absorption interaction types were identified, depending on Δr and the sizes of the defects. The outcomes of these combinations varied, resulting in a perfect $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDL, a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ dislocation loop accompanied by a small SIA cluster, or a $\langle 100 \rangle$

Fig. 9. Schematic of the undisturbed atomic stress fields of a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ loop with 100 SIAs and a C15 cluster with 40 SIAs along the $[111]$ direction, shown for different values of Δl . The stress fields of the two defects were calculated separately and then positioned within the same simulation box to illustrate their interactions at various relative distances.

0) dislocation loop. In some specific cases where the resulting configuration did not exhibit a clear structure at 600 K (up to 6 ns), increasing the temperature to 1000 K often resulted in the formation of a $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ dislocation loop.

3. Confinement: When $A_{lc} = 0$, confinement of the $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ PDL was observed beneath the C15 cluster. This confinement persisted even at elevated temperatures up to 1000 K, indicating a relatively high binding energy between the dislocation loops and the C15 Laves clusters. This indicates that the elastic confinement of $1/2 \langle 111 \rangle$ dislocation loops by C15 clusters could play a role in the stabilization of experimentally observed rafts of dislocation loops, along with other contributing factors.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Amin Esfandiarpour: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declares that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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